

Perceptions and Knowledge of Patients and Dentists towards *Teledentistry* in Indonesia and Other Countries During the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has forced the health sector, including dentistry, to implement new methods of providing healthcare services. One such method is the use of teledentistry. This study aims to determine the perception and knowledge of dentists and patients regarding the use of teledentistry in various countries, including Indonesia, during the COVID-19 pandemic. **Methods:** This study used the rapid review method and focused on articles published between 2020 and 2023. Articles were identified through searches in electronic databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar, using relevant keywords. Articles were selected using the PRISMA method and through a screening process based on predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. **Results:** A total of 1554 articles were found, and 19 articles were selected as research samples. The results showed that the perception and knowledge of teledentistry was generally positive, both according to dentists and patients. **Discussion:** The majority of dentists had good experiences with teledentistry, although there were still doubts about teledentistry's ability to provide accurate diagnoses. Many patients were also satisfied with the experience of using teledentistry, despite technical obstacles such as difficulties in taking good intraoral images or internet connection problems. **Conclusion:** Knowledge and perceptions of teledentistry show considerable variation across countries. This study shows that dentists generally have good knowledge of teledentistry. Dentists' perception of teledentistry is also positive, although there are still doubts about teledentistry. Patients' knowledge of teledentistry increased during the pandemic. Patients also have a good perception of teledentistry, although some patients still experience technical issues. Overcoming these barriers is important in maximizing the use of teledentistry as part of dental health services.

Introduction

The COVID-19 disease had spread globally in early 2020 and was immediately categorized as a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO). The disease is believed to have originated in Wuhan, China, and is caused by the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV or SARS-CoV-2) which causes severe acute respiratory

symptoms [1]. Various countries developed diverse strategies to control the spread of COVID-19 based on economic, cultural, and health system conditions [2]. These strategies include the implementation of strict lockdowns such as school closures, patient contact tracing, mass quarantine and travel and social restrictions [3]. In particular, Indonesia has

More Information

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implemented the Large-Scale Social Restrictions policy in a number of regions that have experienced a significant increase in positive COVID-19 cases [4]. The American Dental Association (ADA) recommends the postponement of all non-urgent dental procedures to reduce the risk of COVID-19 exposure [5]. The Indonesian Ministry of Health has issued a recommendation to restrict face-to-face health services by utilizing information and communication technology in the form of telemedicine [6]. Teledentistry in a COVID-19 scenario focuses on triage, pain or infection management, remote consultation and scheduling of definitive dental care [7]. Teledentistry serves as a screening tool to help dentists make assessments safely and reduce unnecessary procedures [8]. This technology allows collaboration between practitioners to achieve accurate diagnoses and create adequate treatment plans, especially for patients in areas with limited access to dentists or specialists [9]

The increased use of teledentistry during the pandemic has caused various responses from patients to medical personnel, making it important to understand dentists' and patients' perceptions of teledentistry and their opinions about teledentistry, especially during the pandemic. Several studies on the perception and knowledge of teledentistry among patients and dentists during pandemic have been conducted on specific population with incomplete coverage. Based on this description, this study aims to find out a broader picture of the perceptions and knowledge of patients and dentists regarding teledentistry both overseas and in Indonesia during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods

The type of research used is rapid review. The operational definition of perception is a process that is preceded by the process of sensing, which is the process of receiving stimuli by individuals through sensory devices or also called sensory processes and knowledge is all the results of knowing activities related to an object (which can be in the form of something or events experienced by the subject). The research stages were carried out by determining PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome), inclusion criteria, and exclusion criteria. The study involved a population consisting of dentists and patients. No interventions were conducted in this study. The comparison in this study was between overseas and Indonesia, with the outcome being perception and knowledge about teledentistry during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The search for articles was conducted in electronic databases, namely Pubmed, and Google Scholar, using keywords related to the perception and knowledge of dentists and patients and teledentistry during COVID-19. Articles were selected by reading titles related to the topic and then selected using PRISMA (Preferred

Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis). The inclusion criteria chosen in this study were articles using questionnaire media, articles indexed by Scopus or SINTA, articles in Indonesian or English, and articles published in 2020-2023. Articles that were excluded in this study are articles that use the literature review method and articles that were not fully accessible.

Results

A total of 1554 articles were found with 174 articles coming from Pubmed and 1380 articles were found on Google Scholar. A thorough review of all articles and inclusion and exclusion considerations resulted in 11 articles that could not be fully accessed, yielding a final result of 19 articles were selected as research samples (Figure 1). Research samples most commonly found in Pakistan, Saudi Arabia and Indonesia (Table 1 and figure 2).

Figure 1: PRISMA Chart

Figure 2: Number of Articles per Country

Dentist's knowledge of teledentistry (Table 2) showed that dentists had heard of the term teledentistry [10,11,12]. Other showed different result that most of the dentists involved in the study had never heard of the term teledentistry [13,14]. Nassani et al (2021) found that 37.3% of dentists know about teledentistry.13 These results differ from the findings of Raja et al, Subhan et al, and Zahra et al which showed higher knowledge of teledentistry (68.6%-94.7%) [10,15,16]. Most dentists in some studies answered

that they had never practiced teledentistry [16,17]. Different results were found by Plaza-Ruiz et al, and Cheuk et al which showed more doctors had practiced with teledentistry [12,18]. The figure of 49.3% in the study Cheuk et al was obtained from the sum of the number of respondents who had used teledentistry before (13.1%) and after (36.2%) the COVID-19 pandemic.18 Research by Raucci-Neto et al in 2022 found only half of dentists (55%) felt prepared with teledentistry methods [17].

Dentists' perceptions of teledentistry (Table 3) showed that the answer "Yes" to the research of Soegyanto et al, Cheuk et al, Khokhar et al, Al-Khalifa & Al-Sheikh, and Chaudary et al took into account the respondents' agreeable and strongly agreeable answers [19-22]. The "no" answer in the study took into account the answers of disagreement and strongly disagree. Soegyanto et al found 37.8% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that teledentistry can produce an accurate diagnosis [19].

There are five articles that examine knowledge and perceptions with patients as respondents. The majority of respondents to the study Aboalshamat et al (68.6%), Menhadji et al (60.9%), Alamgir et al (69.6%), and Kasuma et al (68.6%) were women [24–27]. This result is different from the study of Bugis et al, where most of the respondents were male (54.04%) [28]. Most of the respondents were educated in the study of Aboalshamat et al (44.3%), and Alamgir et al (86%). Respondents varied in age with the majority of adults aged 20-45 years, with the exception of Menhadji et al's study with a majority aged 45-54 years, and Kasuma et al's study targeting college students [24-26]. As many as 44.3% of the respondents in the Aboalshamat et al study were not employed or retired, and all respondents in the Kasuma et al study were students [24,27] (Table 4 - Appendix).

Patients' knowledge of teledentistry was examined in four articles. Aboalshamat et al revealed that only a small percentage of respondents had heard of teledentistry before COVID-19 (17.1%) [24]. This result contrasts with the research of Alamgir et al, most of whose respondents are familiar with the term teledentistry [26]. Research by Kasuma et al found that there are still many respondents who do not know what teledentistry is (68.62%) [27]. Most of the respondents to the study Aboalshamat et al and Kasuma et al stated that they had never done teledentistry before (90-91%) [24,27]. Most of the respondents Kasuma et al were also unaware that patients could obtain a prescription for medication through teledentistry consultations [27] (Table 5).

Patients' perceptions of teledentistry are observed from three aspects, namely the patient's experience, expectations, and limitations. Most patients have good experience in doing teledentistry. Research conducted by Aboalshamat et al showed that 97% of patients felt understandable by doctors, 94.3% of patients felt that it was easy to communicate through teledentistry, and 94.3% of patients felt safe sending personal information through the application.24 Several other studies have also found similar things [25,27,28]. A different study found by Alamgir et al revealed that only 49.6 % of patients who are satisfied with teledentistry [26]. Most patients also want to reuse teledentistry services at the next meeting [24,27]. Different results were found in the study of Alamgir et al which showed that only 46.4% of patients would return to teledentistry [26]. The limitation found is that many patients feel difficulties in technical problems. These limitations can be in the form of difficulty taking dental pictures, or problems with internet connection.24,26 (Table 6 - Appendix).

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Articles

No.	Title	Author	Year	Country	Contents
1.	Teledentistry: a new oral care delivery tool among Indian dental professionals – a questionnaire study [10]	Raja et al.	2022	India	Dentist knowledge
2.	Role of Teledentistry in COVID-19 Pandemic: A Nationwide Comparative Analysis among Dental Professionals [11]	Abbas et al	2020	Pakistan	- Dentist knowledge - Dentist's perception
3.	Impact of COVID-19 on the Knowledge and Attitudes of Dentists toward Teledentistry [12]	Plaza-Ruiz et al	2021	Colombia	Dentist knowledge
4.	Teledentistry—Knowledge, Practice, and Attitudes of Dental Practitioners in Saudi Arabia: A Nationwide Web-Based Survey [13]	Nassani et al	2021	Saudi Arabia	- Dentist knowledge - Dentist's perception

5.	A national teledentistry study on the knowledge, attitudes, training and practices of private dentists [14]	Girardeau et al	2022	France	Dentist knowledge
6.	Teledentistry as a Supportive Tool for Dentists in Pakistan [15]	Subhan et al	2021	Pakistan	- Dentist knowledge - Dentist's perception
7.	Awareness of Dentists Regarding Use of Tele-Dentistry During Pandemic of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) [16]	Zahra et al	2020	Pakistan	Dentist knowledge
8.	Knowledge, Perception, and Experience of Dentists About Teledentistry [17]	Raucci-Neto et al.	2022	Brazil	Dentist knowledge
9.	Teledentistry use during the COVID-19 pandemic: perceptions and practices of Ontario dentists [18]	Cheuk et al	2023	Canada	- Dentist knowledge - Dentist's perception
10.	Indonesian Dentists' Perception of the Use of Teledentistry [19]	Soegyanto et al	2022	Indonesia	Dentist's perception
11.	Awareness regarding Teledentistry among Dental Professionals in Malaysia [20]	Khokhar et al	2022	Malaysia	Dentist's perception
12.	Teledentistry awareness among dental professionals in Saudi Arabia [21]	Al-Khalifa & Al-Sheikh	2020	Saudi Arabia	Dentist's perception
13.	Teledentistry awareness, its usefulness, and challenges among dental professionals in Pakistan and Saudi Arabia [22]	Chaudhary et al	2022	Pakistan and Saudi Arabia	Dentist's perception
14.	An overview of the knowledge, perception and experience of dentists in Makassar about the utilization of Teledentistry as a Dental Care Media [23]	Samad et al.	2021	Indonesia	Dentist's perception
15.	Accuracy and perceptions of teledentistry in KSA during the COVID-19 pandemic: A single-centre randomized controlled trial [24]	Aboalshamat et al	2022	Saudi Arabia	- Patient knowledge - Patient perception
16.	Patients' and dentists' perceptions of tele-dentistry at the time of COVID-19. A questionnaire-based study [25]	Menhadji et al	2021	English	- Patient knowledge - Patient perception
17.	Patients Self-Reporting of Utilizing Teledental Services During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia [28]	Bugis	2022	Saudi Arabia	Patient perception
18.	Knowledge and Experience of Teledentistry among urban population of Lahore-A Cross-Sectional Study [26]	Alamgir et al	2022	Pakistan	- Patient knowledge - Patient perception
19.	The Application of Teledentistry : an Alternative Dental Service in Pandemic Era [27]	Kasuma et al	2022	Indonesia	- Patient knowledge - Patient perception

Table 2: Dentist's Knowledge of Teledentistry

Yes	Author	Have you ever heard of teledentistry		Knowing what teledentistry is		Have done teledentistry		Readiness to perform Teledentistry	
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
	[10]	87.7%	12.3%	94,7%	5.3%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	[11]	72,4%	27.6%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	[12]	88,47%	11.53%	N/A	N/A	54.95%	45.05%	N/A	N/A
	[13]	38%	62%	37.3%	62,7 %	23.2%	76.8%	N/A	N/A
	[14]	42.9%	57.1%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	[15]	37.5%	62.5%	68.6%	31.4%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	[16]	N/A	N/A	76.9%	23.2%	13.5%	86.5%	N/A	N/A
	[17]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	15%	85%	55%	45%
	[18]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	49.3%	48.7%	N/A	N/A

Table 3. Dentists' Perceptions of Teledentistry

Yes	Author	Teledentistry results in accurate diagnosis		Teledentistry shortens waiting lists		Teledentistry helps educate patients		Teledentistry helps patients in remote areas		Helps monitor the patient's condition		The use of teledentistry in routine dental practice	
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
	[11]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	37.1%	62.9%	N/A	N/A
	[13]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	74.8%	5%
	[15]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	71.1%	28.9%	68.9%	31.1%
	[18]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	25.2%	41%
	[19]	37.8%	25.9%	91,7%	1.4%	94.8%	0.9%	85.2%	4.4%	89.6%	2.1%	N/A	N/A
	[20]	32%	26%	77%	20%	77%	N/A	74%	7%	58%	13%	N/A	N/A
	[21]	31%	31%	71%	8%	80%	3%	82%	6%	74%	5%	N/A	N/A
	[22]	30.7%	25%	87.5%	1.1%	86.4%	3.4%	73.9%	11.4%	61.4%	18.2%	N/A	N/A

9.	[22]	17.6%	18.6%	64.7%	4.9%	86.3%	N/A	75.5%	5.9%	80.4%	2.9%	N/A	N/A
10.	[23]	16.1%	31%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	5.7%	16.1%	N/A	N/A

Table 5: Patient Knowledge of Teledentistry

Yes	Author	Have you ever heard of teledentistry		Knowing what it is Teledentistry		Ever done Previous teledentistry?		Do you know how to get a prescription through teledentistry consultation	
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
1.	[24]	17.1%	82.9%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
2.	[28]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	8.09%	91.01%	N/A	N/A
3.	[26]	90.4%	9.6%	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4.	[27]	N/A	N/A	31.37%	68.62%	9.8%	90.19%	27.45%	72.54%

Discussion

Several studies show that most dentists have heard of teledentistry practice with a percentage ranging from 72.4% to 88.47% [10-12]. There are also studies that have found that most dentists are unfamiliar with teledentistry practices [13-15]. The difference in results can be caused by the time of the study. Subhan et al examined dentists' knowledge of teledentistry before the COVID-19 pandemic, when awareness of teledentistry at that time was not as high as it is today [15]. During the pandemic, some dentists preferred teledentistry because of concerns about contact with COVID-19 [29,30]. In general, dentists' knowledge of teledentistry increases over time. Research by Boanjoy (2023) also revealed an increase in dentists' knowledge of teledentistry [31]. Raja et al found more dentists who had understood teledentistry compared to previous research. Research in 2021 shows fewer dentists have figured out what teledentistry is due to a lack of understanding in the field. Nassani et al in 2021 found dentists' poor knowledge of teledentistry in Saudi Arabia. This can be due to the lack of practical training in this area and the lack of continuing education programs regarding teledentistry [13].

The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered an increase in teledentistry practices with social restrictions. A number of dentists only started implementing teledentistry practices after the pandemic took place [32]. This study found that there are still many dentists who have never done teledentistry even though some already have knowledge about teledentistry. Zahra et al revealed that one of the obstacles is that there are still dentists who do not have access to related facilities or have not used them [16]. Most of the dentists in the Sidabutar study were familiar with the term

teledentistry, but did not understand its form and how it was used [33]. Tantawi et al also revealed that although knowledge of teledentistry is increasing, its use in clinical practice is still limited in some countries [34]. Raucci-Neto also found that more than 80% of respondents in Brazil had never done teledentistry, with some dentists stating that they were not well prepared to do teledentistry [17]. The low adoption rate of teledentistry often occurs because some dentists are reluctant to practice it due to a lack of knowledge and awareness about teledentistry [35]. The use of teledentistry that is complex and different from commonly used methods is also a barrier [35,36]. It takes the development of additional knowledge, training and digital systems expertise to overcome these difficulties [17,36]. Dentists also face concerns about the results of intraoral or video consultations that may differ from the patient's actual oral condition [37]. Dentists' concerns regarding costs and financial expenses, as well as security issues in data exchange between patients and dentists also add to the barriers to the implementation of teledentistry practices [35,36,38].

The use of teledentistry still raises doubts among dentists, especially regarding its ability to produce diagnoses as accurate as face-to-face consultations. Diagnosis in teledentistry is made based on the results of intraoral imaging or video consultations that can differ from the patient's real oral condition [37]. Dentists can also only see two-dimensional images which can make diagnosis more difficult [39]. This doubt is reinforced by several studies showing that only a small percentage of respondents think teledentistry is capable of producing accurate diagnoses [19-22]. The accuracy of the diagnosis through teledentistry

depends on the quality of the equipment used, the quality of the images obtained, as well as the training of the dentist. Accurate teledentistry results can be achieved with proper training for dentists and adherence to a set of established protocols [20-22]. There are several studies that reveal good teledentistry accuracy in screening and diagnosis [40,41].

Teledentistry provides virtual access to dental care, which can reduce the need for patient visits to the clinic. This approach can shorten patient waiting times at dental health facilities and can save costs and travel time for patients, providing an efficient and practical solution in the provision of dental health services [42]. A number of studies show that the majority of doctor. Dental assesses that teledentistry helps shorten patient waiting lists proving the effectiveness of teledentistry in speeding up treatment and avoiding treatment delays [19-22]. Research by Wallace et al and Kanani et al supports the perception of the ability of teledentistry to shorten waiting lists and wait times in clinics [42,43]. More than 70% of dentists also think teledentistry helps patients in remote areas. Teledentistry can help with access to remote areas that are unreachable due to lockdown policies [29]. In the context of information exchange, the majority of dentists feel helped by teledentistry in providing patient education [19-22]. Most of the respondents to Maqsood et al's study also expressed similar sentiments [29]. Most dentists also recognize that teledentistry facilitates monitoring of patients' conditions [15,19-22]. However, a study conducted by Abbas et al in Pakistan found that 62.9% of respondents felt teledentistry did not help to monitor the patient's condition in depth. These results differ from some other studies conducted in Australia that support the idea that teledentistry can monitor the patient's condition. The study also mentioned the advantages of teledentistry regarding time and cost [44].

Teledentistry is considered a strategy to manage health while maintaining a safe distance and limiting contact with patients [45]. In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, Teledentistry can be a solution to reduce exposure to the virus while still being able to evaluate the condition of patients, especially patients who live in hard-to-reach areas, or for patients who cannot visit the clinic in person [22]. The use of teledentistry in routine practice can be in the form of teleconsultation, telediagnosis, teletriage, and telemonitoring [36]. Teledentistry can also help to conduct an initial examination of the patient's condition to determine whether a referral to a specialist is necessary [43]. The results of several studies show that the majority of dentists agree with the use of teledentistry in routine practice [13,15]. Opposite results were found by Cheuk et al in their study which showed that only 25.2% of dentists agreed that teledentistry was part of routine care [18].

This study examined five articles that examined patients as subjects [24-28]. Respondents were dominated by women except in the Bugis study where the majority of respondents were men. The patients involved were generally aged 20-40 years [25,26,28]. Different age groups were found in the study of Kasuma et al that involved a more specific age group with students as respondents [27]. Most of the respondents had a bachelor's education background [24,26]. Research in Saudi Arabia and research in Indonesia found that respondents' level of knowledge about teledentistry is still low [24,27]. This is in contrast to the findings in Pakistan in 2022 which found that most respondents were familiar with teledentistry even though their level of knowledge was still low [26]. The level of knowledge in Alamgir et al's study was higher because the research was more up-to-date compared to the other two studies [26]. It also reaffirms the challenges of increasing awareness and acceptance of teledentistry in various regions. Teledentistry is gradually beginning to be accepted by patients and healthcare providers as the acceptance of telemedicine increases [34]. The increasing availability of the internet and the development of devices have made the use of telemedicine increasingly relevant in society [46]. Research by Kasuma et al. and Bugis found that the majority of respondents have never used teledentistry services which can be due to the respondents' lack of knowledge or awareness of teledentistry including knowledge about the possibility of obtaining a prescription after consultation [27,28]. Lack of face-to-face communication with dentists leads patients to worry that the results of their problems examination are inaccurate [36]. Patients need to know that teledentistry can help with a detailed evaluation before prescribing patients, making it more time and cost-effective [42]. This study showed that there was no correlation between respondents' knowledge of teledentistry and respondents' gender or age. Respondents' education level had a more close correlation with their knowledge of oral health [27]. In general, patients have high levels of satisfaction and positive experiences with teledentistry [24-28]. Patients feel comfortable communicating with the dentist and feel that they can be understood well [24]. Bugis found that some patients feel that teledentistry can achieve effective communication, although 42% of respondents think that face-to-face communication is more effective. Effective communication and trusting between dentists and patients are essential in reducing anxiety and improve the quality of dental care [47,48]. Dentists should provide patients with information about the advantages and disadvantages of online consultations. Islam et al said online dental care is only used when there is a direct connection between the dentist and the patient and a combination of online and

face-to-face care by the same dentist is required [48]. The study also shows that many patients choose teledentistry for reasons of convenience and better access [25,28]. Rahman et al revealed that patients think that teledentistry can save travel time, waiting time, costs, and make it easier to access health services [49,50].

Research by Aboalshamat et al revealed that patients feel safe sending personal information and images through the app (WhatsApp) [24]. This can be caused by dentists who often communicate with patients through social media, and the use of the WhatsApp application which is quite popular. Most patients are able to make appointments on the clinic's virtual platform, although 23.2% of patients can only do so occasionally [26]. The majority of patients are satisfied with the use of teledentistry and feel benefited and helped by teledentistry [24-28]. As many as 82.35% of patients in the study Kasuma et al also felt that teledentistry was effective in the COVID-19 pandemic. Similar results were obtained by Amtha et al. which showed a high level of satisfaction in oral disease patients with teledentistry services during the COVID-19 pandemic [51].

Various studies show that patients' expectations for teledentistry are diverse. There is a high enough satisfaction with the use of teledentistry that the majority of patients are willing to use this service again [24,27]. Menhadji et al also found that most patients felt the ease in the online appointment making process. Bugis' research shows divided patient expectations. 52.63% chose phone dental service for dental consultation, and 63% of patients chose face-to-face meetings for diagnosis [28]. The research of Alamgir et al showed lower expectations with only a fraction of patients willing to use teledentistry again [26]. Griffith et al in their study of orthodontic patients found that most patients preferred face-to-face meetings and argued that teledentistry was only used to improve communication, not as a substitute for face-to-face consultations [52].

The difference in expectations and perceptions of teledentistry is inseparable from various limitations that still need to be addressed. Aboalshamat et al found that many respondents (54.3%) had difficulty taking quality dental imaging [24]. Nearly half of patients (48.6%) also experienced internet connection issues during teledentistry sessions that could hinder effective communication between dentists and patients [24]. Alamgir et al found a number of patients (19.2%) experienced technical impairments that interfered with the ability to hear and speak clearly during teledentistry sessions [26]. Estai explained that there are several other obstacles that need to be addressed in the use of teledentistry in the form of patient knowledge and concerns, difficulties in using technology, and internet

access problems [53]. Research also revealed patients with lower socioeconomic power had a higher likelihood of facing problems when using teledentistry [24].

Conclusion

Knowledge and perceptions of teledentistry show diverse variations in different countries. This study shows that generally dentists have good knowledge of teledentistry. Dentists' perceptions of teledentistry are also positive, although there are still doubts about teledentistry diagnoses. Patients' knowledge of teledentistry increased during the pandemic. Patients also have a good perception of teledentistry, and most want to use it again, although some patients still experience technical issues that interfere with communication with the dentist. Overcoming technical barriers and increasing understanding and awareness of teledentistry practices is essential in maximizing the use of teledentistry as part of dental health services so that teledentistry can be part of the future of dental health care and accessible to all walks of life. Further research can be done by focusing on the use of teledentistry post-pandemic.

References

1. Kumar G, Rehman F, Al-Muzian L, Farsi D, Hiremath S. Global Scenario of Teledentistry during COVID-19 Pandemic: An Insight. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent* [homepage on the Internet] 2021; 14(3):426–429.
2. Chen H, Shi L, Zhang Y, et al. Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic: Comparison of Strategies in Six Countries. *Front Public Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2021;9:708496.
3. Wang X, Shi L, Zhang Y, Chen H, Sun G. Policy disparities in fighting COVID-19 among Japan, Italy, Singapore and China. *Int J Equity Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2021; 20(1):33.
4. Mufida S, TFGC, WSD. The Indonesian Government's Strategy in Handling the COVID-19 Outbreak from an Economic Perspective. *Independent: Indonesian and Global Political Journal* 1 2020; 2:121–130.
5. Alsafwani Z, Shiboski C, Villa A. The role of telemedicine for symptom management in oral medicine: a retrospective observational study. *BMC Oral Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 22(1):92.
6. Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. Circular Letter of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number HK.02.01/MENKES/303/2020 concerning the Implementation of Health Services through the Utilization of Technology and Communication in the Context of Preventing the Spread of Corona Virus (COVID-19). 2020;
7. Chopra SS, Sahoo NK. Protocol for teledentistry during COVID-19 in Armed Forces dental establishments. *Med J Armed Forces India* [homepage on the Internet] 2020; 76(3):356–359.

8. Macapagal J. Applications of Teledentistry during the COVID-19 Pandemic Outbreak. *Applied Medical Informatics* 2020; 42:133–141.
9. Tella AJ, Olanloye OM, Ibiyemi O. Potential of teledentistry in the delivery of oral health services in developing countries. *Ann Ib Postgraduate Med [homepage on the Battle of the Internet]* 2019; 17(2):115–123.
10. Raja KP, Pal A, Nayak SU, Pai K, Shenoy R. Teledentistry: a new oral care delivery tool among Indian dental professionals - a questionnaire study. *F1000Res [homepage on the Internet]* 2022;11:666.
11. Abbas B, Wajahat M, Saleem Z, Imran E, Sajjad M, Khurshid Z. Role of Teledentistry in COVID-19 Pandemic: A Nationwide Comparative Analysis among Dental Professionals. *Eur J Dent [homepage on the Internet]* 2020; 14(S 01):S116–S122.
12. Plaza-Ruiz SP, Barbosa-Liz DM, Agudelo-Suárez AA. Impact of COVID-19 on the Knowledge and Attitudes of Dentists toward Teledentistry. *JDR Clin Trans Res [homepage on the Internet]* 2021; 6(3):268–278.
13. Nassani MZ, Al-Maweri SA, AlSheddi A, et al. Teledentistry-Knowledge, Practice, and Attitudes of Dental Practitioners in Saudi Arabia: A Nationwide Web-Based Survey. *Healthcare (Basel) [homepage on the Internet]* 2021; 9(12).
14. Giraudeau N, Bauer M, Tramini P, Inquimbert C, Toupenay S. A national teledentistry study on the knowledge, attitudes, training and practices of private dentists. *Digit Health [homepage on the Internet]* 2022;8:20552076221085068.
15. Subhan R, Ismail WA, Musharraf S, Khan M, Hafeez R, Alam MK. Teledentistry as a Supportive Tool for Dentists in Pakistan. *Biomed Res Int [homepage on the Internet]* 2021;2021:8757859.
16. Zahra SFT, Yousaf A, Akram H, Sajjad T, Bangash KA, Yousaf N. Awareness of Dentists Regarding Use of Tele-Dentistry During Pandemic of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal [homepage on the Internet]* 2020; 70(2).
17. Raucci-Neto W, Souza Pereira M de, Cerqueira NM, Louzada VG, Castro Raucci LMS de, Leoni GB. Knowledge, Perception, and Experience of Dentists About Teledentistry. *Int Dent J [homepage on the Internet]* 2021; 72(4):456–462.
18. Cheuk R, Adeniyi A, Farmer J, Singhal S, Jessani A. Teledentistry use during the COVID-19 pandemic: perceptions and practices of Ontario dentists. *BMC Oral Health [homepage on the Internet]* 2023; 23(1):72.
19. Soegyanto AI, Wimardhani YS, Maharani DA, Tennant M. Indonesian Dentists' Perception of the Use of Teledentistry. *Int Dent J [homepage on the Internet]* 2022; 72(5):674–681.
20. Khokhar RA, Ismail WA, Sunny A, et al. Awareness regarding Teledentistry among Dental Professionals in Malaysia. *Biomed Res Int [homepage on the Internet]* 2022;2022:3750556.
21. Al-Khalifa KS, AlSheikh R. Teledentistry awareness among dental professionals in Saudi Arabia. *PLoS One [homepage on the Internet]* 2020; 15(10):e0240825.
22. Chaudhary FA, Ahmad B, Javed MQ, et al. Teledentistry awareness, its usefulness, and challenges among dental professionals in Pakistan and Saudi Arabia. *Digit Health [homepage on the Internet]* 2022;8:20552076221089776.
23. Samad R, Pasiga BD, Nuryamsi, Aryanto A. An overview of the knowledge, perception and experience of dentists in Makassar about the utilization of teledentistry as a dental care media. *Journal of Dentomaxillofacial Science* 2021; 6(3):180–183.
24. Aboalshamat KT, Althagafi TK, Alsaedi SA, Alhumaidi SN, Alemam AA. Accuracy and perceptions of teledentistry in KSA during the COVID-19 pandemic: A single-centre randomised controlled trial. *J Taibah Univ Med Sci [homepage on the Internet]* 2022; 17(3):506–515.
25. Menhadji P, Patel R, Asimakopoulou K, et al. Patients' and dentists' perceptions of tele-dentistry at the time of COVID-19. A questionnaire-based study. *J Dent [homepage on the Internet]* 2021;113:103782.
26. Alamgir W, Khan UJ, Haider A, Babar P, Yousuf R. Knowledge and Experience of Teledentistry among urban population of Lahore - A Cross-Sectional Study. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences [homepage on the Internet]* 2022 [cited 2024 Jan 24]; 16(12).
27. Kasuma N, Nurwidyastuti P, Lestari C, Nismal H, Murniwati. The Application of Teledentistry : an Alternative Dental Service in Pandemic Era. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research [homepage on the Internet]* 2022; 15(2):699–706.
28. Bugis BA. Patients Self-Reporting of Utilizing Teledental Services During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia. *J Patient Exp [homepage on the Internet]* 2022;9:23743735221112210.
29. Maqsood A, Sadiq MSK, Mirza D, et al. The Teledentistry, Impact, Current Trends, and Application in Dentistry: A Global Study. *Biomed Res Int [homepage on the Internet]* 2021;2021:5437237.
30. Ahmed MA, Jouhar R, Ahmed N, et al. Fear and Practice Modifications among Dentists to Combat Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Outbreak. *Int J Environ Res Public Health [homepage on the Internet]* 2020; 17(8).
31. Boanjoy SM, Setiawan AS, Suryanti N. Development of dentists perceptions and knowledge of teledentistry. *Indonesian Dental Magazine; Vol 9, No 2 (2023): August 2023;*
32. Sycinska-Dziarnowska M, Maglitto M, Woźniak K, Spagnuolo G. Oral Health and Teledentistry Interest

during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *J Clin Med* 2021;10:3532.

33. Sidabutar M, Simamora FD, Mahastuti SAP. Readiness of Dentists towards Teledentistry Applications During Covid-19 Pandemic in East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research* 2023; 16(2):668–674.

34. Tantawi M El, Lam WYH, Giraudeau N, et al. Teledentistry from research to practice: a tale of nineteen countries. *Frontiers in Oral Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2023;4.

35. Smith AC, Thomas E, Snoswell CL, et al. Telehealth for global emergencies: Implications for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Telemed Telecare* [homepage on the Internet] 2020; 26(5):309–313.

36. Ghai S. Teledentistry during COVID-19 pandemic. *Diabetes Metab Syndr* [homepage on the Internet] 2020; 14(5):933–935.

37. Deshpande S, Patil D, Dhokar A, Bhanushali P, Katge F. Teledentistry: A Boon Amidst COVID-19 Lockdown—A Narrative Review. *Int J Telemed Appl* [homepage on the Internet] 2021;2021:8859746.

38. Silva HEC da, Santos GNM, Leite AF, et al. The role of teledentistry in oral cancer patients during the COVID-19 pandemic: an integrative literature review. *Support Care Cancer* [homepage on the Internet] 2021; 29(12):7209–7223.

39. Fahim A, Saleem Z, Malik KA, et al. Exploring challenges and mitigation strategies towards practicing Teledentistry. *BMC Oral Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 22(1):658.

40. Queyroux A, Saricassapian B, Herzog D, et al. Accuracy of Teledentistry for Diagnosing Dental Pathology Using Direct Examination as a Gold Standard: Results of the Tel-e-dent Study of Older Adults Living in Nursing Homes. *J Am Med Dir Assoc* [homepage on the Internet] 2017; 18(6):528–532.

41. Gurgel-Juarez N, Torres-Pereira C, Haddad AE, et al. Accuracy and effectiveness of teledentistry: a systematic review of systematic reviews. *Evid Based Dent* [homepage on the Internet] 2022;

42. Kanani H, Khubchandani M, Dangore-Khasbage S, Pandey R. Teledentistry: A Comprehensive Review and Its Application in Pediatric Dental Care. *Cureus* [homepage on the Internet] 2024; 16(1):e52685.

43. Wallace CK, Schofield CE, Burbridge LAL,

O'Donnell KL. Role of teledentistry in paediatric dentistry. *Br Dent J* [homepage on the Internet] 2021;

44. Poirier B, Jensen E, Sethi S. The evolution of the teledentistry landscape in Australia: A scoping review. *Australian Journal of Rural Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 30(4):434–441.

45. Mahdavi A, Atlasi R, Naemi R. Teledentistry during COVID-19 pandemic: scientometric and content analysis approach. *BMC Health Serv Res* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 22(1):1111.

46. Giudice A, Barone S, Muraca D, et al. Can Teledentistry Improve the Monitoring of Patients during the Covid-19 Dissemination? A Descriptive Pilot Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2020; 17(10).

47. Yuan S, Freeman R, Hill K, Newton T, Humphris G. Communication, Trust, and Dental Anxiety: A Person-Centred Approach for Dental Attendance Behaviours. *Dent J* 2020;118.

48. Islam MRR, Islam R, Ferdous S, et al. Teledentistry as an Effective Tool for the Communication Improvement between Dentists and Patients: An Overview. *Healthcare* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 10(8).

49. Rahman N, Nathwani S, Kandiah T. Teledentistry from a patient perspective during the coronavirus pandemic. *Br Dent J* [homepage on the Internet] 2020;

50. Emami E, Harnagea H, Shrivastava R, Ahmadi M, Giraudeau N. Patient satisfaction with e-oral health care in rural and remote settings: a systematic review. *Syst Rev* [homepage on the Internet] 2022; 11(1):234.

51. Amtha R, Gunardi I, Astoeti TE, Roeslan MO. Satisfaction Level of the Oral Medicine Patients Using Teledentistry During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Factor Analysis. *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent* [homepage on the Internet] 2021; 11(4).

52. Griffeth JK, Shroff B, Carrico C, Cook P, Lindauer SJ. Patient perspectives on teledentistry and face-to-face doctor interaction during orthodontic treatment. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics* [homepage on the Internet] 2023; 163(3):328–337.

53. Estai M, Kruger E, Tennant M, Bunt S, Kanagasingham Y. Challenges in the uptake of telemedicine in dentistry. *Rural Remote Health* [homepage on the Internet] 2016; 16(4):1–5.

Appendix

Table 4: Demographics of the Patients of the Study Respondent

No.	Article	Gender		Education				Patient Age	Jobs			
		Male	Women	Elementary - Junior School	High School	School Upper Middle	Bachelor		Postgraduate	Students	Employees	Not working or retiring
1.	[24]	31.4%	68.6%	8.6%		38.6%	44.3%	8.6%	N/A	22.9%	32.9%	44.3%
2.	[25]	39.1%	60.9%	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	45-54% aged 45-54 years old	N/A	N/A	N/A
3.	[28]	54.04%	45.96%	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	62.98% are old 25-44 years old	N/A	N/A	N/A
4.	[26]	30.4%	69.6%	N/A		N/A	86%	9.6%	96% are 20-40 years	N/A	N/A	N/A
5.	[27]	31.37%	68.63%	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100%	N/A	N/A

Table 6: Patient Perception of Teledentistry

Yes	Author	Title	Results		
			Experience	Expectations	Limitations
1.	[24]	Accuracy and perceptions of teledentistry in KSA during the COVID-19 pandemic: A single-centre randomised controlled trial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 97% felt doctors understood them correctly - 94.3% found it easy to communicate via teledentistry - 94.3% felt safe sending personal information and pictures through an app (WhatsApp) 	88.6 % would use teledentistry services again	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 54.3% had difficulty taking dental pictures - 48.6% experienced internet connection issues during teledentistry sessions
2.	[25]	Patients' and dentists'	- 75% felt comfortable with online	- 83.4% agreed that making	N/A

		perceptions of tele-dentistry at the time of COVID-19. A questionnaire-based study	appointments - 87.1% were helped by consultation through Teledentistry	online appointments easy - 84.9% found appointment instructions easy to follow	
3.	[28]	Patients Self-Reporting of Utilizing Teledental Services During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia	- 57.14% were more satisfied with phone dental service - 42.76% more satisfied with virtual dental service - 42.11% felt that the availability of access is easier to use phone dental service - 42.11% found effective communication with doctors easier through face-to-face services	- 52.63% chose Phone Dental Service for dental consultation - 52.63% chose face-to-face services for dental diagnosis	N/A
4.	[26]	Knowledge and Experience of Teledentistry among urban population of Lahore-A Cross-Sectional Study	- 30% answered that they can make an appointment on the virtual clinic platform once in a while - 49.6% satisfied with teledentistry	46.4% would use teledentistry services again at another meeting	19.2% answered that they could rarely hear and speak without being bothered by technical problems
5.	[27]	The Application of Teledentistry : an Alternative Dental Service in Pandemic Era	- 82.35% answered consultations via teledentistry effectively during the COVID-19 pandemic - 94.11% felt benefited by the use of teledentistry methods	98.03% wanted to use the teledentistry method again at another meeting	N/A

